

USING TAGUCHI'S STATISTICAL METHOD FOR OPTIMIZING CO-INJECTED BIOCHAR COMPOSITES

Matthew J. Zaverl¹, M. Misra^{1,2*}, A. K. Mohanty^{1,2}

¹School of Engineering, Thornbrough Building, University of Guelph, Guelph, N1G 2W1, Ontario, Canada, ²Bioproducts Discovery and Development Centre, Department of Plant Agriculture, Crop Science Building, University of Guelph, Guelph, N1G 2W1, Ontario, Canada

* Corresponding author(mmisra@uoguelph.ca)

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1.1 Introduction

Injection molding of polymers has been steadily growing in the past decade because of its fast cycle time, low production costs, and reliability. Most conventional polymers used in injection molding are obtained from petroleum feedstocks. The current trend of oil consumption has been regarded as an unsustainable practice, thus inducing a push for alternatives from petroleum usage. Biopolymers are a rapidly growing field that aims at reducing the amount of petroleum used in polymer applications, as well as relieving landfills with biodegradability. The widespread industrial use of biopolymers has been severely limited due to their prices and properties. To allocate these differences, researchers can add agriculturally sourced bio-fibers or blend polymers together for improvements in performance and reduction in costs. This research is one of the first to analyze the effects of adding BioChar as cost effective bio-based filler. Biochar is created from the pyrolysis of bio mass. Farmers often improve the fertility of their soil by increasing the carbon content through the addition of BioChar.[1] BioChar is an important filler to consider such that it can be sourced from crop residue and other agricultural wastes thus making it easy and cheap to obtain. The research aims at co-injecting a strong brittle core of poly(trimethylene terephthalate) (PTT) and poly(butylene terephthalate) (PBT) with BioChar that is encased by a tough biodegradable skin of

poly(butylene succinate) (PBS) with poly(butylene adipate-terephthalate) (PBAT).

1.2 Injection Molding

The injection molding process was first patented in 1872, and underwent a massive growth during World War II with the demand of mass-produced products that were easy to make and low in cost. [2] The Injection molding unit consists of a large screw set that can be modified for specific purposes. The screw set rotates in a contained space known as a barrel. This barrel has heating elements attached to it which allow for added polymer to reach a molten state under the added heat. The barrel can consist of many different heating zones. Each of these zones is set to a specified temperature which is maintained throughout the process. The polymer is usually fed into the barrel by a hopper. Hoppers in an industrial setting are linked to a much larger silo that continuously feeds the injection machine. The raw is melted and mixed within the barrel to be forced through a nozzle at the end of the barrel and into a mold where it freezes in the shape of its mold. There are many different variations and setups that can be produced obtained from this basic setup.

Once the proper setup is obtained engineers then look towards the intrinsic properties of the injection molding process. The first consideration is shear rate. Shear rate is given by equation 1. [2]

$$SR = \frac{D * N}{h} \quad (1)$$

Where SR is shear rate, D is screw diameter, N is screw rotation rate, and h is depth of channel. Shear rate is an important property in regards to the degradation of the polymer melt. Each polymer has a corresponding critical shear rate, in which it begins to degrade within the barrel of the injection unit. From equation 1 it is evident that once a screw size is chosen, engineers can only control the screw rotation rate to ensure a polymer does not reach its degradation point.

With the raw polymer being successfully melted and pushed through the injection unit without obtaining degradation from the shear rate the focus is now placed on the molding unit. This mold unit has a very simple purpose, which is to clamp the two sides of a cavity mold together during the melt transfer process. A set amount of force is required to hold the two mold sides together. Too little of force and the injected polymer will escape from the mold cavity. Too much force and the engineer run the risk of damaging the mold.

There are a number of parameters that can be varied to have an effect on the molding process. To analyze every possible variable is a time consuming and endless project. It is however much agreed throughout literature that the main processing parameters can be simplified to those that fall under the domain of temperature, pressure, time, and mold design. Temperature effects are largely characterized by the melt temperature and mold temperature. The melt temperature is the temperature of the polymer exiting the injection unit nozzle. This temperature is a defining factor in the way the

polymer behaves while being injected. A polymer that has absorbed a great amount of heat energy will become less viscous and will flow relatively faster than if it was colder. A degree of care must be taken by the engineer to ensure that the polymer does not heat up too much or else it will begin to degrade and lose its properties.

Mold temperature is another aspect of temperature effects on injection molding. Once a polymer melt is injected into the mold it immediately begins to cool down and freeze into a solid shape. By controlling the temperature of the mold surface engineers can manipulate the amount of time it takes for the melt to solidify. This is a requisite for large molds that require the polymer melt to cover large areas before solidifying. The cooling rate for a polymer melt can also have a definitive effect on the final mechanical properties of the molded shape.

Pressure is another major property that has a large effect on the outcome of an injection molded part. During the injection process there is two types of pressure. The initial pressure is the force that is used to push the polymer melt through the nozzle and into the mold. The engineer is trying to optimize the use of the highest available pressure and the lowest injection time to transfer the melt. This will ensure the smallest cycle time, which has an economical benefit, and ensures that the melt solidifies evenly, rather than over a prolonged time period due to the absence of material. The second pressure effect is known as holding pressure. This is the pressure that is applied after the mold has been filled with the melt. This pressure is used to ensure that the injected material stays compact while it takes the shape of the mold.

Time is another important property in the injection molding process. Much of timing has to do with the barrel time. This is the amount of

time a polymer is contained by the screws within the barrel. A proper amount of time is required to ensure that the polymer is fully melted and ready to be pushed into the mold. If the polymer remains within the heated barrel with rotating screws for too long it will quickly degrade. Injection time is also a critical parameter for the formation of a properly molded sample. A fast injection time is desired however too fast of an injection time will result in a poorly filled mold, while a slow injection time will allow the initial melt to solidify before the mold is fully filled, resulting in a non-uniform product. Holding pressure ensures that the polymer is fully solidified before being released from the mold. Each polymer has a specific temperature at which it can be released without risking deformation to that part. This is known as the Heat Deflection Temperature (HDT). Materials with high HDTs are valued for their ability to decrease the cycle times by requiring less time within the mold to solidify.

Mold design is the last of the parameters and is subdivided into geometries of the mold. Runners are lengths of conduits channels used within the mold to transfer the polymer melt evenly across the mold cavities. Longer runner lengths can disrupt the flow of the polymer melt and thus have significant effects on the crystallization rate of the polymer. Longer runners require the help of hot runners. These are the same runners that have heating elements behind them that allow the runners to have a hotter temperature than the rest of the mold. This in turn reduces the heat loss as the polymer melt is transferred from the injection sprue to the mold cavity.

1.3 Co – Injection Molding

Co - Injection molding (CIM) which can otherwise be known as sandwich injection molding is an injection technique that utilizes two separate polymer components.[3] The two polymer materials are sequentially injected. The

first material is injected to partially fill the mold, this material is then pushed to the outside of the mold due to the incoming second material, and a final shot of the first material is used to close up the sample.

The CIM machine has the same setup as the single injection machine with an additional second unit that holds the second material as seen in figure 1. The Co-Injection method is an advanced method of injection molding that requires the fine tuning of many processing parameters for the production of quality molded parts. The core material is often chosen to reduce the costs of the overall part, and is either foamed or sourced from recycled material where scrapped material can be reused in the core while virgin material is utilized on the outer layer of the formed parts.[5]

Much of the literature that has been performed on mapping CIM effects have generally concluded that the parameters with the largest effect on CIM included, injection speed, injection pressure, melt temperature, and mold temperature. These parameters have a direct or indirect effect on the viscosity and flow of the two polymeric materials. In an encompassing study Young et al., (1980) linked the ratio of the two polymers viscosity to the uniform distribution of skin thickness around the core.

They reported that when the viscosity ratio of the core material over the skin material was equal, a uniform skin thickness was achieved. Core breakout is when the inner material pushes through the skin material and is generally attributed to having low viscosity ratio. Likewise having low core penetration length is generally attributed to having too high of a viscosity ratio. [4] The specified viscosity ratio range that has been regarded as the range of successful co-injection is reported to be from 0.5 to 5. [6]

$$0.5 < \frac{v_{core}}{v_{skin}} < 5 \quad (2)$$

While much of the industrial applications for CIM include using recycled or foamed cores, CIM presents engineers with a unique opportunity to produce finely customized material solutions for certain applications. Since there are two layers in the molded part, combinations of material properties can be utilized. The skin material forms the surface properties of the part including, impact strength, chemical resistance, texture, and printability. While the core material makes up the structural properties such as tensile and flexural strength and modulus. In comparison, the popular method of blending materials combines two separate polymers into one homogeneous product. Thus CIM allows engineers to utilize certain required properties from each material without having to mix them together, which is sometimes detrimental to the required material property.

As described above in the first section, this research is focused on utilizing biopolymers or renewably resourced polymers for CIM. By taking advantage of the two layer system the bio-content, which is usually restricted due to performance issues, can be easily increased with careful material selection. For this research a blend of poly(butylene terephthalate) (PBT) and poly(trimethylene terphthalate) (PTT) is used as the core material. The skin material is a blend of tough biodegradable polymers consisting of poly(butylene succinate) (PBS) with poly(butylene adipate-terephthalate) (PBAT).

PTT is a partially biobased (37 wt%) semi crystalline linear aromatic polyester with three methylene units in the chemical structure. It is synthesized by the condensation of 1, 3 – propanediol with terephthalic acid. PTT shares similar mechanical properties to poly(ethylene terphthalate), while having a comparable

processing characteristics to PBT. PTT's glass-transition temperature (T_g) is in the range of 42-75^oC, and has a melting temperature around 228^oC which is very close to that of PBT (roughly 225^oC). [7] Zhang, J. [7] has reported PTT's dependency on mold temperature. Indicating that it has a major effect on the final properties.

PBT is also a semi crystalline linear aromatic polyester and shares the same carbon backbone as PTT however PBT has four methylene units. It is synthesized with 1, 4 – butanediol and terephthalic acid. PBT is widely used for electrical components as it has high strength, low moisture absorption, very high electrical insulation properties, high temperature capabilities, and is easy to mold with fast cycle times. The PBT used in this study is not biobased. Very recently Toray Industries Inc. in partnership with Genomatics Inc., have announced that they will be producing a biobased PBT on a commercial scale using 1, 4-butanediol (BDO) as a feedstock. [8]

PBAT is an aliphatic–aromatic copolyester. It is an extremely tough polymer that is used as a flexible plastic for films and extrusion coating [9] PBAT is also biodegradable prompting many researchers to explore its toughening abilities in biodegradable biobased materials. PLA/PBAT and PHBV/PBAT blends were shown to decrease tensile strength and modulus, however, elongation and toughness dramatically increased. [9][10] Currently small batches of biobased PBAT are in production but are quickly growing in size. This project uses petroleum based PBAT.

PBS is another tough polymer which can be used in many applications due to its good processability. [10] It can be injected, blown, and extruded into various yarns, sheets, and products. PBS is made from succinic acid and is petroleum based, however recent advancements

in succinic feedstock have allowed PBS to be produced from bio resources, making PBS a new biobased polymer. This study utilizes petro based PBS in the hopes of being able to replace it with biobased product when it becomes more readily available.

1.4 BioChar

To increase the biocontent of the overall part the core blend of PTT/PBT is mixed with a biomass to create a biocomposite. This biomass is known as BioChar. BioChar is the byproduct of pyrolyzed biomass. In this process biomass is heated up in the absence of oxygen. When this occurs the normal reaction of carbon dioxide is hindered and the remaining biomass carbon is either released as a bio-oil or sequester it into a solid comprised largely of carbon. Ancient civilizations in the Brazilian Amazon were noted for producing BioChar some 3000 years ago for fertilizing their soil. Recently BioChar has been gathering a renewed interest for its beneficial effects on the environment. The ability to sequester atmospheric carbon absorbed by the plants and retain it into the soil is especially interesting. Gaunt and Lehmann, (2008) analyzed the energy balance and emissions associated with BioChar sequestering and pyrolysis for bioenergy production. In their study they showed that CO² emissions are reduced 2-5 times when the bioenergy byproduct biochar is applied to fertilizer applications. They further explain that if the biochar production is optimized by using lower heat, the energy output is 30% less, however, the resulting energy is still 2- 7 times greater than that provided by ethanol. [11] During fast pyrolysis the temperature is heated at a rate > 1000 °C/min to final temperatures greater than 500°C, while for slow pyrolysis the biomass is heated at a rate of 300°C/min to a final temperature around 300°C. In slow pyrolysis gas is the major constituent, while bio-oil is the major constituent for fast pyrolysis. For both methods BioChar is the

second largest byproduct with yield ranging from 15 to 40%. [12] This research is novel in its exploration of BioChar as a composite material. The benefits of BioChar have yet to be explored. One direct benefit of BioChar is that the nature of its production ensures that BioChar can be used in engineering plastics without thermal degradation, as the processing temperatures of these plastics are often greater than 200°C.

1.5 Factorial Design

With the many options of parameter levels it can be confusing for the researcher to optimize the process. Any numbers of parameters that are usually considered in single injection molding are theoretically tripled when trying to understand the CIM of two separate materials, each of the two units have their own parameters as well as the interaction effects between the two materials must also be considered. Thus researchers must consider much more than a simplified parameter effects profile. A Factorial design of experiments is produced to assess the significance of the main processing parameters, along with interaction effects between two different parameters.

2 Materials

For this study PBT was supplied by Ticona in Florence, Kentucky under the trade name Celanex grade 2000-3. PTT was supplied by DuPont in Delaware, USA under the trade name Sorona. PBS (Biocosafe-2003) and PBAT

Biocosafe – 2007) were both supplied by Xinfu from China. The extruded materials and neat polymers were dried overnight at 80°C before processing. BioChar was supplied by Alberta Agriculture and Rural Affairs. It was sourced from wheat straw.

3 Methods

The factorial design of experiments is created as a 16 experimental run, two level five factor half

factorial design L_{16} (2^5), which would allow interaction effects to be studied up to three-way interactions. Factors include, melt temperature (skin and core), mold temperature, injection speed, and injection pressure.

The core and skin material were prepared by feeding neat pellets into a Leistritz co-rotating intermeshing twin screw extruder (MIC 27/aL-48) with a strand die. For the core material neat pellets of PBT and PTT were hand mixed at a 30 to 70 wt.% ratio respectively with 10 wt.% BioChar as filler, before being mixed in the extruder. PBS and PBAT were also hand mixed at a ratio of 60 to 40 wt.%. The molding was done in a 77 ton AURBURG (Model No: 370 S 700-290/70, Germany) two component injection molding machine, capable of both single and co-injection. Screw diameter in unit 1 is 35 mm with a temperature profile of 6 heating zones, while unit 2 screw diameter is 22 mm with 5 heating zones. All single injections were done using unit 1. While unit one was used for core material and unit 2 was used for skin material during the CIM. The screw speed, injection time, and backpressure were maintained constant throughout all of the trials.

4 Results and Discussion

Figure 2 outlines the basic modulus findings of the PBT/PTT (30/70) blend versus PBT/PTT/BioChar (27/63/10%) and the co-injected 60%.vol [PBS/PBAT (60/40%.wt)] + 40%.vol [PBT/PTT (30/70%.wt)]. It can be seen that as expected there is an increase in modulus upon the addition of the brittle biochar. These properties are easily manipulated by changing the thickness ratios between the skin and core.

Conclusion

For this study the co-injection of co-injected 60 vol.% [PBS/PBAT (60/40 wt.%) + 40 vol.% [PBT/PTT/BioChar (27/63/10 wt.%)] was performed to understand the potential properties available to the material makeup. The authors

present a design of experiments that is to be used in hopes of better mapping the effects that the processing parameters have on the final specimen properties. The properties observed in the presented data set suggest that a core profile that is too small will result in a sample with poor tensile and flexural properties, while a thick skin profile develops specimens with large impact strengths. It is up to the engineer or scientist to develop a proper skin to core ratio to obtain a desired property.

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Figure 1: Schematic overview of co-injection molding. I) Skin material is injected first into the mold cavity. II) The second material is injected behind the skin material. Fountain flow occurs, with the second material pushing the first material forwards and to the sides of the mold. The cold surface of the mold causes the first material to freeze. III) After the second material has been fully injected a finishing shot of the first material is used to close off the sample.

Figure 2: mechanical moduli for blended composites and co-injected polymer blends. A - PBT/PTT (30/70%wt), B- 10%wt BioChar (Wheat Straw)+ 90%wt [PBT/PTT(30/70%wt)] C- 60%vol [PBS/PBAT (60/40%wt)] + 40%vol [PBT/PTT (30/70%wt)]